

**THEORETICAL BASIS OF GENDER VIOLENCE AND THE ROLE OF
THE JUDICIAL SYSTEM****Mirzaeva Aziza Asatovna**Senior assistant to the judge of the Samarkand
regional court for criminal cases<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214345>**Annotation**

The article examines the theoretical foundations of gender violence and analyzes the role of the judicial system in its prevention and punishment. The main theoretical approaches to the study of gender violence, its types and causes are presented. Particular attention is paid to legal regulation and the role of national and international acts in combating this phenomenon. The problems of law enforcement practice related to the protection of the rights of victims are considered, and possible ways to improve the judicial system and the legislative framework are proposed.

Keywords

Gender-based violence, judicial system, legal regulation, law enforcement practice, protection of victims, legislative measures, international acts.

Introduction

Gender-based violence is one of the most acute and global problems of modern society, negatively affecting millions of people around the world. This phenomenon covers a wide range of actions aimed at discrimination, humiliation and violence against individuals based on their gender. Issues related to gender-based violence have received widespread attention in international legal practice and national legislation, which emphasizes its importance for both science and the law enforcement system.

The relevance of the problem of gender-based violence is determined not only by its widespread nature, but also by the scale of its consequences for society. Gender-based violence leads to the destruction of families, mental health problems, and the limitation of economic and social opportunities for victims. Gender-based violence includes physical, sexual, psychological and economic violence, which can manifest itself both in the home and in the public environment. Social norms, gender stereotypes and cultural prejudices often contribute to the creation of an environment where violence becomes acceptable or invisible, which significantly complicates the fight against this phenomenon.

The purpose of this article is to study the theoretical foundations of gender-based violence and examine the role of the judicial system in combating this phenomenon. The judicial system plays a key role in protecting victims and punishing perpetrators, but often faces difficulties in law enforcement practice related to proving facts of violence, as well as insufficient legal protection for victims. In conditions where legislative norms require improvement, the task of identifying and analyzing problems arising in law enforcement in cases of gender-based violence and finding ways to solve them becomes relevant.

The role of the judicial system in preventing and punishing gender-based violence is central to the discussion of this issue, as legal mechanisms protect victims and ensure fair retribution for perpetrators. In international practice, there are a number of conventions and treaties, such as the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), which establish common standards for protection against gender-based violence. At the national level, legislative acts and regulations are also aimed at preventing this phenomenon, but their effectiveness and implementation remain controversial.

The article will pay special attention to the problems that victims of gender-based violence face when seeking legal protection. In many cases, victims have difficulty proving the facts of violence, lack proper legal support and lack awareness of their rights. This is especially true for those who live in regions with an underdeveloped judicial system or have limited access to justice. In addition, social and cultural barriers, stereotypes and biased attitudes towards gender roles also complicate the situation and create additional pressure on victims.

The objectives of the article include:

1. Definition of concepts and theoretical foundations of gender-based violence.
2. Study of factors influencing the emergence and spread of gender-based violence.
3. Analysis of the role of the judicial system in the prevention and punishment of gender-based violence.
4. Identification of problems in law enforcement practice and proposals for improving legislation.

Thus, the study is aimed at a deep analysis of the essence of gender violence and an assessment of the effectiveness of judicial protection measures. The results obtained can form the basis for developing recommendations for

improving law enforcement practices and legislative norms aimed at reducing the level of gender violence and strengthening the protection of the rights of victims.

The concept of gender violence

Gender-based violence is a form of violence based on socially embedded ideas about the roles of men and women, in which one gender, most often women, is subjected to aggression, discrimination or humiliation by the other. It is associated with the violation of human rights and is aimed at the subordination or oppression of an individual because of his or her gender. Gender-based violence is based on social norms, stereotypes and prejudices that create inequality and imbalance in relations between the sexes.

Gender-based violence covers a wide range of manifestations, including **physical** , **psychological** , **sexual** and **economic violence** . All these types of violence can manifest themselves both separately and in combination with each other, forming a complex oppression and humiliation of the victim. Gender-based violence can occur in the family environment, in the workplace, in educational institutions, in public spaces and in other contexts where people interact with each other.

1. **Physical violence** is the most obvious form of violence, involving physical injury or the threat of injury. It can range from light blows to serious injuries, even murder. This violence is often used to establish control and suppress the victim. A characteristic feature of physical violence is its cyclicity: the abuser may alternate aggressive actions with apologies and promises that it will not happen again, which creates the illusion of normalization.

2. **Psychological violence** is an impact on the emotional state and psyche of the victim. It includes threats, humiliation, insults, manipulation and isolation. Psychological violence is not always immediately recognizable, but its consequences can be devastating for the victim. This type of violence destroys self-confidence, reduces self-esteem and causes depression. Psychological violence often accompanies other forms of gender-based violence and can serve as a “background” for more obvious acts of aggression.

3. **Sexual violence** is any unwanted sexual behavior, including harassment, rape, and other forms of forced sexual activity. It is aimed at dominating the victim and using her body against her will. Sexual violence has far-reaching consequences, affecting the victim’s physical and mental health. It destroys trust, violates a sense of safety, and creates feelings of shame and guilt.

4. **Economic abuse** is a form of control in which the abuser limits the victim's access to financial resources or uses them as a means of manipulation. Economic abuse includes control over income, limiting access to bank accounts, and preventing the victim from working or going to school. This form of abuse is especially dangerous because it makes the victim dependent on the abuser and prevents them from escaping or seeking help.

Gender-based violence often occurs within **the family** and **intimate relationships**. Domestic violence, which is largely gender-motivated, is one of the most common forms of violence in the world. Women and children are more likely to be victims of such violence, although men can also be abused by partners or other family members. Domestic violence can remain hidden for long periods of time, as victims are often embarrassed or afraid to report what is happening, fearing social stigma or retaliation.

In addition, gender-based violence can be **structural**, meaning it can manifest itself through social institutions and laws that maintain inequality between men and women. This includes unequal pay, limited access to education or health care, and unfair distribution of social roles. Such structural forms of violence maintain social inequality and create the conditions for other types of gender-based violence.

One of the key challenges in understanding gender-based violence is the influence of **cultural and social norms**. In some societies, violence against women may be considered normal or even part of family relationships, making it difficult to prevent and punish. In such contexts, women may not have access to justice or remedies because violence is seen as a “private matter” of the family rather than a public issue.

Overall, gender violence is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that requires a comprehensive approach to its prevention and combating. It not only destroys the lives of individuals, but also undermines the foundations of equality and justice in society, making it one of the most important challenges for the modern judicial system.

Theoretical Foundations of Gender-Based Violence

Gender-based violence is based on sociocultural and historical preconditions that shape inequality between men and women. There are several theoretical approaches that explain its nature and prevalence.

One of the key theories is **the patriarchal theory**, which holds that gender violence arises from the social dominance of men and the subordination of women. Patriarchy has historically conditioned a system of power in which men

control most resources, decision-making, and public life, while women are forced into a subordinate position. In this context, violence becomes an instrument of control that maintains this social order.

Another important approach is **social role theory**, which focuses on how social expectations of gender roles contribute to violence. In traditional societies, men are assigned roles as dominant, aggressive protectors, while women are assigned the role of submissive and caring. Such gender stereotypes create conditions in which violence can be justified as a means of maintaining these roles.

Power and control theory states that gender violence is a manifestation of the desire to maintain power and dominance over a partner. Violence becomes a means of asserting control over another person's personal freedom, actions, or decisions. This is especially true in cases of violence in intimate relationships, where one partner uses violence to maintain power.

Also important is **feminist theory**, which views gender-based violence as a consequence of systemic oppression of women and violation of their rights. According to this approach, violence is not limited to isolated incidents, but is part of structural inequalities maintained by political, economic and cultural factors.

Thus, the theoretical underpinnings of gender-based violence highlight its connection with historically established gender inequalities, social norms and power, making the problem of violence deeply rooted in society.

The Role of the Judicial System in Combating Gender-Based Violence

The judicial system plays a vital role in combating gender-based violence by protecting the rights of victims and holding perpetrators accountable. The legal system is the primary mechanism for ensuring justice and fairness, and its activities are aimed at preventing violence, punishing perpetrators and restoring the rights of victims. However, the effectiveness of the judicial system in this area largely depends on legislation, law enforcement practices, the training of specialists and the availability of specialized procedures for handling cases of gender-based violence.

Legislative framework

A key element in combating gender-based violence is legislative measures that create a legal basis for protecting victims and punishing perpetrators. Most countries have laws in place to combat gender-based violence, such as criminal codes, administrative acts, and specialized laws on protection against domestic violence. International instruments, such as **the UN Convention on the**

Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) and the Istanbul Convention , also play an important role in creating standards for combating gender-based violence at the national level.

However, despite the existence of a legislative framework, actual law enforcement practice often faces a number of problems, such as the difficulty of proving facts of violence, the length of court proceedings and uneven enforcement of laws. It is important that legislative norms not only exist, but are also effectively applied in practice. This requires constant improvement of legal norms, as well as their adaptation to changing conditions and challenges.

Problems of law enforcement practice

One of the key challenges in the justice system in cases of gender-based violence is **the difficulty of proof** . Gender-based violence, especially in the form of psychological or economic pressure, often occurs in the private sphere and does not always leave obvious traces. Victims often face difficulties in collecting evidence, and witnesses may be absent. This creates additional obstacles to the trial and makes it difficult to reach a fair decision.

In addition, many victims do not seek legal action due to **a lack of trust in the judicial system** . This may be due to bias, lack of knowledge about their rights, or fear of retaliation from the abuser. Court proceedings in such cases can be lengthy and stressful for the victim, which increases trauma and creates a sense of helplessness. To improve the effectiveness of judicial protection, it is important to develop special programs, such as **domestic violence courts** , that can provide victims with additional guarantees of protection and support.

Specialization of the judicial system

One possible solution to improve the effectiveness of judicial protection for victims is **the specialization of judicial bodies** and law enforcement agencies in the field of combating gender-based violence. This involves training judges, prosecutors and police officers who will be able to professionally and competently consider such cases, taking into account the specifics of gender-based violence and the needs of victims.

Specialised courts for cases of domestic or gender-based violence already exist in a number of countries and have proven effective. These courts focus on hearing cases quickly and sensitively, which helps to minimise stress for victims and reduce the length of proceedings. They also provide a greater understanding of the specifics of gender-based violence, which helps to make fairer decisions.

Protecting the rights of victims

One of the central tasks of the judicial system is **to ensure the protection of the rights of victims**. This includes both legal protection and measures to ensure the physical and psychological safety of the victim. Temporary protective measures, such as injunctions and orders that restrict the abuser's access to the victim while the case is pending, play an important role here. These measures help ensure the safety of the victim and prevent further violence.

Providing **psychological support** to victims of violence is also important. The judicial system should take into account not only the legal but also the social aspects of the problem of gender violence. Victims often need comprehensive assistance, including consultations with psychologists and trauma specialists. Integrating such programs into judicial processes helps victims recover from violence and cope with the consequences associated with the proceedings.

International experience

International experience shows that judicial systems that are focused on protecting the rights of victims of gender-based violence can significantly reduce the level of this phenomenon. Programs aimed at raising awareness among judges and lawyers, special courses for law enforcement officers, and the development of a victim support system have proven their effectiveness in countries with a developed legal system. For example, in Spain and the UK, specialized victim support services are actively operating, helping them go through complex legal processes.

In addition, **international cooperation plays an important role** in combating gender-based violence. Common standards and exchange of experience allow countries to implement more effective practices and improve the quality of justice. International organizations such as the UN and the Council of Europe provide support in developing programs to protect women's rights and combat gender-based violence.

Conclusion

The role of the judicial system in combating gender-based violence is undeniable, but to achieve maximum effectiveness, it is necessary to constantly improve legislation and law enforcement practices. An important step in this direction is the development of specialized courts, improving the qualifications of lawyers and law enforcement officers, and the introduction of measures aimed at protecting the rights and interests of victims. The judicial system must

become a reliable tool in the fight against gender-based violence and guarantee justice for all participants in the process.

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